

Policy Report on Generative Artificial Intelligence

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This fellowship ran from January-May 2023 as part of BRAID. An extended version of this report is available here:

<https://dl.acm.org/doi/abs/10.1145/3600211.3604722>

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This research was supported via UK Research and Innovation by the R&D Science and Analysis Programme at the Department for Culture, Media & Sport. Any primary research, subsequent findings or recommendations do not represent Government views or policy and are produced according to research ethics, quality assurance, and academic independence.

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● ● ● Executive Summary

Key Findings

Our study is based on a comprehensive literature review of text-to-image generative models, identifying four high-priority risks associated with generative artificial intelligence (AI):

1. **At-scale production of discriminatory content.**
2. **At-scale toxic and harmful (mis)use.**
3. **Rapid and cheap production of misinformation and disinformation.**
4. **Privacy and copyright infringement.**

Recognising the importance of a well-informed and holistic approach to AI development and regulation, we show how the UK's pro-innovation framework for AI regulation can be adapted to regulate generative AI models and offset the aforementioned risks.

We propose that the UK's financial support for generative AI model development aligns with the regulatory recommendations outlined in this report. Specifically, we recommend that a portion of this investment should be allocated to the implementation of socio-technical safeguards that mitigate the high-priority risks.

We argue that establishing strong connections among academic, policy, and regulatory institutions is essential for effective knowledge sharing and application. This ensures that the integrity of all knowledge forms is maintained, contributing to a well-rounded and informed strategy for generative AI development and regulation.

● ● ● 1. Background

The rapid advancement of artificial intelligence (AI) presents significant opportunities to transform various sectors of public and private life, across innovative business development, healthcare, education, and the creative arts. The United Kingdom of Great Britain and Northern Ireland (UK), currently ranked third for investment, innovation, and implementation in AI technologies (Tortoise media, 2022), is committed to taking a leading role in the development and adoption of AI worldwide (OECD.AI, 2023).

The UK is a thriving hub for world-renowned AI research labs, such as DeepMind, and is the birthplace of unicorn AI companies, including Stability AI, OneTrust, Graphcore, and Thought Machine, as well as a host of promising AI startups. A recent government report reveals that 3,170 AI companies call the UK home, collectively generating £10.6 billion in AI-related revenue since 2016 (Department for Science Innovation and Technology and Office for Artificial Intelligence, 2023). As the socio-economic influence of AI begins to expand, recent government initiatives, including the £900 million development of supercomputers to train advanced generative AI models and a £125 million investment in building a global network and furthering AI research, are set to propel the nation even further into the forefront of AI innovation.

AI technologies, while brimming with potential, can also bring about transformative negative consequences for society. Numerous ethics and governance reports (for example, the AI Now Institute's annual report and Ethics Guidelines for Trustworthy Artificial Intelligence prepared by the European Commission's High-Level Expert Group on AI), academic papers and conferences (e.g. FAccT and AIES), and forums (e.g. Global Partnership on AI) have been dedicated to discussing and addressing the ethical, safety, and social challenges posed by AI systems. An open letter, dated 29 March 2023 and endorsed by over 1,000 prominent computer scientists, highlights concerns about the adverse implications of generative AI models and urges AI labs to suspend the training of powerful generative AI systems for a minimum of six months.

Regardless of the letter's effectiveness in proposing meaningful action, it underscores the growing concern surrounding the potential deep negative impacts of these systems on people's lives.

To ensure that AI research and development leads to societal betterment while mitigating high-risk adverse effects, it is important to establish and adapt regulatory mechanisms and frameworks in response to emerging AI systems. This policy report examines a specific case study concerning state-of-the-art generative AI technologies, such as Stable Diffusion, in order to extract recommendations on how to regulate the development and deployment of generative AI models.

The UK government has adopted a "pro-innovation" framework for AI regulation, founded on five key principles: (i) safety, security, and robustness; (ii) appropriate transparency and explainability; (iii) fairness; (iv) accountability and governance; and (v) contestability and redress. This report integrates the case study into the existing framework, fostering further discourse based on the current literature ([A pro-innovation approach to AI regulation - GOV.UK \(www.gov.uk\)](https://www.gov.uk/government/consultations/a-pro-innovation-approach-to-ai-regulation)).

Generative AI models, including text-to-text large language models (LLMs) and text-to-image models (TIMs), have advanced remarkably in recent years. Capable of synthesising various data modalities to produce hyper-realistic outputs, these models serve as the foundation for applications such as conversational chatbots, exemplified by San Francisco-based startup OpenAI's ChatGPT, and text-to-image systems, such as London-based Stability AI's Stable Diffusion. These innovative models present a plethora of exciting opportunities. However, they also introduce potential risks and harms that have captured the attention of the AI ethics and safety community. Consequently, it is vital to navigate the development and implementation of such technologies with prudence and foresight.

Our policy report examines the UK's pro-innovation framework for AI regulation, specifically focusing on its specialisation in and implementation of generative AI models. We explore the high-level risks and harms related to the deployment and use of modern generative AI models, using TIMs as a prime example, while also acknowledging the applicability of our findings to other models, such as LLMs. Our investigation begins by identifying stakeholders impacted by the deployment and use of these models. Subsequently, we present a taxonomy of high-priority risks and harms specific to each stakeholder group. Our taxonomy is rooted in a comprehensive literature review. We then offer policy proposals and regulatory mechanisms to govern these risks.

● ● ● 2. Stakeholders

The literature identifies the following key stakeholders as being impacted by the technologies that are built on generative AI models. Their engagement is vital for the success of policy recommendations (see Figure 1).

- **Data source:** This refers to individuals whose created work is incorporated into the training data sets, such as photographers or digital artists.
- **Data subject:** This pertains to individuals who appear in training data, such as images, making them the focus or subjects of the content used in developing and refining generative AI models.
- **Developers:** These include organisations and individuals responsible for various aspects of generative AI model creation, such as coding, development, training, and testing, ensuring that the models are both effective and reliable.
- **Commercial users:** These models are employed in various commercial applications such as design, digital asset creation, and stock imagery generation. Commercial users are responsible for implementing generative AI models in a manner that aligns with the guidelines within their respective industries.

- **Research users:** Text-to-image models may be utilised to train ‘downstream’ technologies, such as robot vision systems, enabling advancements in research and development across multiple fields.
- **Hobbyists:** Casual users, including those generating art and graphics, may use these models for personal enjoyment or creative expression. However, some users may also create malicious content, such as explicit or harmful imagery.
- **Affected parties:** Marginalised individuals are likely to be most impacted by misrepresentation in model output, lack of access to technology, and the consequences of work precarity. Creatives and models may face job displacement due to AI-generated content. Public figures, journalists, businesses, and institutions are also at risk of disinformation efforts stemming from the misuse of generative models.

● ● ● 3. Key Risks

To see a summary of our empirically grounded literature review, see Table 1.

3.1 At-scale Generation of Discriminatory Content

Extensive work has been undertaken to show that generative AI models can output wrongful discriminatory information due to learned information from the training data, including problematic sexual, racial, and cultural stereotypes (See Ackermann & Li, 2022; Qiu et al, 2022; Millière, 2022a; Newton & Dhole, 2023; Hutchinson et al, 2022; Bianchi et al, 2022; Dev et al, 2022, i.a.). Research shows that generative models, through the facilitation of image and text generation at scale, could result in the furthering of particular political agendas by generating biased outputs.

Existing work focuses on biased output stemming from biased data sets, but there are a number of other ways in which discrimination could manifest, for example the harsher impact of increased job precarity on marginalised people; people’s inability to

access the model due to speaking a dialect; and the exploitation of moderation workers by powerful tech companies.

Figure 1. Stakeholders

Risk	Stakeholders	References
Discrimination & Exclusion		
Cultural and racial bias	Users, Affected	Hutchinson et al. (2022); Millière (2022a); Yu et al. (2022); Bianchi et al. (2022); Cho et al. (2022)
Gender and sexuality bias	Users, Affected	Millière (2022a); Newton and & Dhole (2023); Hutchinson et al. (2022); Bianchi et al. (2022); Cho et al. (2022)
Class bias	Users, Affected	Bianchi et al. (2022)
Disability bias	Users, Affected	Bianchi et al. (2022)
A loss of work for creatives, models	Sources, Users	Newton & Dhole (2023); Ghosh & Fossas (2022); Oppenlaender (2022)
Religious bias, ageism etc.	Users, Affected	-
Dialect bias	Users	-
Pre-release moderation	Developers, Affected	-
Toxic & Harmful (mis)Use		
Sexual images	Subjects, Users, Affected	Millière (2022a); Hutchinson et al. (2022); Yu et al. (2022)
Sexualising images of children	Subjects, Users, Affected	Wolfe et al. (2022)

Hateful, violent or taboo content	Developers, Users, Affected	Hutchinson et al. (2022); Brack et al. (2022); Millièrè (2022a); Struppek et al. (2022)
Misinformation & Disinformation		
Likeness reproduction	Subjects, Users, Affected	Millièrè (2022b); Mishkin et al. (2022); Nichol et al. (2022); Rombach et al. (2022); Jursenas et al. (2021); Somepalli et al. (2022)
Misleading harmful content	Users, Affected	Nguyen et al. (2022); Boswald & Saab (2022); Beyer & Boswald (2022); Brady (2020); Franks & Waldman (2019); Paris & Donovan (2019); Gamir-Ríos et al. (2021); Tomasev et al. (2022); Jankowicz et al. (2021); Nichol et al. (2022); Widder et al. (2022)
Fraud and scams	Users, Affected	Khoo et al. (2022); Beyer & Boswald (2022); Paris & Donovan (2019); Verdoliva (2020); Mathews et al. (2023)
Detection and classification bias	Developers, Subjects, Users, Affected	Xu et al. (2022); Nadimpalli & Rattani (2022); Lovato et al. (2022); Pu et al. (2022); Radford et al. (2021)

Polarisation	Users, Affected	Akers et al. (2019); Giomelakis et al. (2021); Beyer & Boswald (2022); Brady (2020); Coeckelbergh (2020); Lovato et al. (2022)
Flooding	Users, Affected	Boswald & Saab (2022)
Miscommunication	Developers, Users, Affected	Yu et al. (2022); Hutchinson et al. (2022)
Democratic integrity	Users, Affected	Coeckelbergh (2020); Westerlund (2019); Vaccari & Chadwick (2020); Lovato et al. (2022)
Social, economic integrity	Users, Affected	Boswald & Saab (2022); Westerlund (2019); Bateman (2020); Bremmer & Kupchan (2023); Akhtar (2023)
Privacy & Copyright Issues		
Privacy infringement	Sources, Subjects	Carlini et al. (2023)
Copyright infringement	Users, Sources	Carlini et al. (2023); Somepalli et al. (2022); Vyas et al. (2023)

Table 1. Risk Taxonomy

3.2 At-Scale Production of Toxic and Harmful (mis)Use

Generative models have been used to automate the generation of harmful content. For example, research found a high number of sexualised images (30%+) produced by a Stable Diffusion model for prompts mentioning girls as young as 12 years old (neither of the models they tested produced more than 11% sexualising images of boys for any age) (Wolfe et al, 2022). There is a risk of deliberate misuse to create sexually objectifying images of young people. Searching for “girl” on promptbase.com, a marketplace for prompts, returns a large number of sexualised images with childlike features.

The improved realism of output images merits review of their legal status. Our research has shown that certain cultural taboos may be inadvertently broken by a TIM’s output, and that it may be hard to predict the offensiveness of an image from the input text due to such texts typically being under-specified (Hutchinson et al, 2022) (for example, a practising Muslim may be depicted drinking alcohol by a model prompted with “a hijabi having a drink”). It is not hard to stretch the imagination and consider malicious users launching websites and media outlets for disseminating problematic content of this sort.

There are a number of ways (in addition to the exploitation of model risks identified above) in which users might deliberately produce harmful content, for example by circumventing existing safety guardrails. Research has shown that it is easy to inject “backdoors” into TIMs such that they act normally except in response to specific prompts, resulting in the generation of harmful images. They demonstrate that it is possible to train a “poisoned” text encoder (that can be shared with other developers over the internet) that reacts to certain trigger characters by producing unwanted images (Struppek et al, 2022).

3.3 Rapid and Cheap Production of Misinformation and Disinformation

We discuss the harms of misinformation and disinformation at three scales: individual, social, and community.

3.3.1 Individual Harms

Personal harms of misinformation and disinformation can target individuals or groups of people. We consider individual harms in terms of misinformation, such as likeness reproduction. Many individual harms cause emotional distress, and their representations of subjects can be disparaging or pejorative.

Research has shown that non-consensual likeness reproduction or people-centric uses of TIMs represent a primary harm (see Yu et al, 2022; Mishkin et al, 2022; Rombach et al, 2022; Nichol et al, 2022). Other individual harms can include fake journalism profiles (Khoo et al, 2022), blackmail and revenge (Hansen, 2022; Nour & Gelfand, 2021), or identity theft for fraudulent purposes (Akhtar, 2023; Mathews et al, 2023).

The reinforcement of existing cognitive biases (Akers et al, 2019) using AI-enabled misinformation can amplify narratives of otherness (Gamir-Ríos et al, 2021; Tomasev et al, 2022) by unifying and legitimising the beliefs of groups with related world views, and supporting negative and false views about others. These risks can engender racist or xenophobic action against the “other”. These efforts are enabled by social misinformation risks such as “flooding”, as discussed below.

The harms identified here impact affected parties, as seen in the targeting of female public figures within synthetically generated porn. Efforts to mitigate disparagement of identities using misinformation also requires developers to reduce abilities, such as likeness preservation and “not safe for work” content generation.

3.3.2 Social Harms

In addition to the harms discussed at the individual level, misinformation and disinformation efforts can degrade social networks and exacerbate polarisation. Algorithmic curation in online social networks (“filter bubbles” Pariser (2011)), anonymity and immediate, vast reach (Akers et al, 2019) enables the dissemination of TIM misinformation to receptive and primed audiences. Siloed communities such as closed networks of Facebook users who see self-similar political content develop a lack of tolerance, increased closure to new information and amplified attitude polarisation (Lazer et al, 2018; Giomelakis et al, 2021).

Misinformation and disinformation within closed circles is especially dangerous as it avoids formal fact checking efforts (Brady, 2020) or diverse “herd correction” effects (Lovato et al, 2022). This can be especially dangerous in times of crisis, such as the COVID-19 pandemic (Rocha et al, 2021). As such, victims of this risk may be those who rely on non-traditional media and closed communities for news, such as Facebook or Whatsapp (Trauthig, 2022), or who engage with low credibility news sources and may be resistant to fact checking (Saltz et al, 2021).

AI-enabled misinformation and disinformation efforts can impact aspects of epistemic agency (Coeckelbergh, 2020). Loss of true signal, or the “flooding” of information environments (Brady, 2020; Boswald and Saab, 2022), degrades our ability to decipher truth from fiction, thus creating doubts in others, society, democratic systems and our epistemic capabilities (Boswald and Saab, 2022; Coeckelbergh 2020). This also allows for the proliferation of bad actors who can take advantage of the “liars dividend” (Chesney and Citron, 2018).

3.3.3 Community Harms

The social harms related to communication and persuasion can cause harm to the integrity of economies, societies and democracies. We label community harms as both representational and allocative as they are intertwined with individual and social

representational harms (e.g misleading content → polarisation → social disruption), however their consequences are allocative.

The allocation of a stable democracy, society and financial system can be threatened by AI-enabled misinformation and disinformation. The creation and dissemination of misinformation disproportionately affects marginalised communities who may be vulnerable to democratic and social instabilities or have fewer data protections.

Generative AI models can also present risks to political institutions, threaten the integrity of democratic discourse (Brady, 2020) through election interference (Westerlund, 2019; Akhtar, 2023), enable state actors to work on a larger scale and to create “evidence” to legitimize fake news, persecute or convince. AI can enable easy propaganda creation (Newton and Dhole, 2023; Westerlund, 2019), permitting malicious actors to generate versions of propaganda, quickly cherry-pick and effectively distribute (Mishkin et al, 2022). These actions will eventually reduce trust in institutions (Jursenas et al, 2021) and destroy democratic agency (Coeckelbergh, 2020).

Some researchers claim that TIM misinformation can influence financial markets and disrupt economies (Raval et al, 2022; Akhtar, 2023; Lovato et al, 2022) and heighten risks of war and state violence (Nguyen et al, 2022; Boswald and Saab, 2022).

AI-enabled misinformation and disinformation also present particular risks in times of crisis (Lovato et al, 2022), where evidence can be manufactured to suit partisan narratives.

3.4 Privacy and Copyright Issues

Carlini et al. (2023) find that both Stable Diffusion and Imagen output images identical to source images, and Somepalli et al. (2022) find that in addition to duplication, Stable Diffusion will replicate content in part.

The reproduction of sensitive images being reproduced is a major risk to privacy (LAION, used to train Stable Diffusion, contains leaked private medical information) (Carlini et al, 2023). This duplication may also mean work by marginalised creators is effectively stolen and sold by companies offering text-to-image output as a service: Carlini et al. (2023) found 35% of images duplicated by Stable Diffusion fall under explicit non-permissive copyright notice.

Somepalli et al. (2022) warn of the risks of “digital forgery”. The authors of this policy paper were able to find models trained on particular artists shared online. Text-to-image models may also be employed for a form copyright “laundering” – if it is decided images generated by a text-to-image model belong to the prompt provider, models and prompts might be engineered to “steal” particular images. The risks of privacy and copyright infringement directly impact a number of stakeholders including data sources and subjects, who may have their rights violated; users, who may steal content, perhaps unintentionally; and regulators, who must untangle the complex legal status of source and output images.

● ● ● 4. Policy Proposals & Pro-innovation Regulation

We present our policy recommendations within the context of the UK’s pro-innovation regulatory framework as follows.

Principle 1: To enhance safety, security, and robustness, we propose the establishment of a multistakeholder and multi-faceted benchmark for the fair, safe, and robust

evaluation of generative models, such as LLMs and TIMs, emphasizing the mitigation of problematic discriminatory content. Additionally, we recommend requiring documentation of generative AI model development through the use of model cards and data cards.

Safety, Security, and Robustness

1. Demand the establishment of a multi-stakeholder and multi-faceted benchmark for fair, safe, and robust evaluation of generative models, such as LLMs and TIMs, with special consideration for mitigating discriminatory content.
2. Demand the need for documenting the development of generative AI models by model cards and data cards.

Principle 2: To ensure appropriate transparency and explainability, we suggest implementing relevant Explainable AI tools to effectively capture system opacity. Moreover, it is vital to properly formulate transparency demands for specific application contexts and communicate the limitations of Explainable AI tools.

Appropriate Transparency and Explainability

1. Ensure relevant Explainable AI tools are employed to capture the opacity of systems properly.
2. Ensure the demands of transparency for a particular context of application are correctly formulated and the limitations of Explainable AI tools are communicated.

Principle 3: For improved accountability and governance, we advocate enforcing both internal and external audit mechanisms. Furthermore, we emphasise the importance

of adhering to privacy laws and data protection acts in order to prevent potential data leaks.

Accountability and Governance

1. Enforce internal and external audit mechanisms.
2. Ensure a privacy laws and the data protection act are respected in the face of possible data leaks.

Principle 4: To promote fairness, we recommend integrating digital and media literacy into educational programs and social education, enabling users to better understand the limitations and potential risks associated with generative AI models like TIMs. Additionally, we propose the development of novel safeguards to prevent the creation and dissemination of inappropriate or harmful texts and images, particularly those of a discriminatory or violent nature.

Fairness

1. Integrate digital literacy and media literacy into educational programs and social education for everyone to help users understand the limitations and potential risks associated with generative AI models such as TIMs.
2. Develop novel forms of safeguards to prevent the creation and dissemination of inappropriate or harmful texts and images, especially those that are discriminatory and violent in nature.

Principle 5: To address contestability and redress, we suggest clearly communicating to users when their data will be used to train generative models like TIMs, as well as discussing the benefits and risks of developing these models. It is also crucial to ensure

that copyright ownership is clearly identified and respected when generating images from text, along with establishing clear rules for attribution and usage.

Contestability and Redress

- Clearly communicate to users when their data will be used to train TIMs, and consult the benefits and risks of developing these models.
- Ensure that copyright ownership is clearly identified and respected when generating images from text, and establish clear rules for attribution and usage.

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<https://dl.acm.org/doi/abs/10.1145/3600211.3604722>

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This research was supported via UK Research and Innovation by the R&D Science and Analysis Programme at the Department for Culture, Media & Sport. Any primary research, subsequent findings or recommendations do not represent Government views or policy and are produced according to research ethics, quality assurance, and academic independence.

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